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The Emergence of Hybrid Warfare and the Future of Global Security: A Comparative Study of Russian and NATO's Hybrid Infrastructure in Ukraine

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Shahzada Rahim Abbas

Department of International Relations, Ibn Haldun University, Turkey
rahim.abbas@stu.ihsu.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9242-5131>

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ABSTRACT

The paper discusses the dynamical nature of fifth-generation warfare, which is gradually becoming a new way of waging war. In the past two decades, there has been a fierce debate on the nature and methods of fifth-generation warfare across the international security forums. Within these discussions, the term “Hybrid warfare” has grabbed the attention of various security experts. Although the discourse of “Hybrid warfare” initially emerged in the mainstream sphere during the 2006 Lebanon war, it gained prominence after the Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014, which triggered debates on the nature of warfare in the 21st century. Russian President Vladimir Putin’s Military doctrine “Escalate to de-escalate” is very clear about the Russian red line for NATO expansion on the Eastern European shores that aims at least aggression with maximum gains. The article enquires about the wider analytical and historical notions of security to sum up the discussion on the new military strategies and tactics on security. The Russian operation in Ukraine with hybrid warfare methods will be the focal point of the discussion throughout the article. The article will also discuss the well-established hybrid warfare infrastructure of Russia vis-à-vis NATO to further elaborate on the discourse of modern armed conflict. To theoretically explore the topic, this study will consider the growing challenges to international security amidst the hybrid warfare settings through the lens of strategic theory.

“I know not with what weapon World War-III will be fought, but World War-IV will be fought with sticks and stones”

Albert Einstein¹

¹ This quote is commonly associated with Albert Einstein, though the exact source is uncertain and often debated. It likely stems from a 1948 letter or interview where Einstein discussed the devastating potential of nuclear weapons, implying that a third world war could reduce civilization to primitive conditions.

Introduction

Russia annexed Crimea in 2014, with little aggression and a legitimate referendum in the peninsula, where 90% ethnic Russians voted for the annexation of Crimea by Russia. Since then, the context of warfare has widely changed, and the discussion on the term “hybrid Warfare” has significantly increased in the security domain across Europe (Popescu, 2015). The discussion has triggered a global debate, prompting security experts and researchers to engage in extensive dialogue on the internet to understand the context of this emerging phenomenon. Moreover, these intensified discussions across various forums have elucidated the potential new dynamics of warfare in the twenty-first century with the involvement of multiple actors (Giegerich, 2016) and new methods that have condemned the traditional notion of war and peace in the context of armed conflict (Reichborn-Kjennerud and Cullen, 2016).

Although the initial discussions concerning the notion of hybrid warfare remained limited, in recent years, it has emerged as a major contention of academic inquiry among academicians and security experts. (Baumann, 2020). The situation has also alarmed NATO, particularly due to the use of hybrid tactics in Ukraine, prompting them to engage in deliberate consultations aimed at enhancing defence capabilities to prevent hybrid outbreaks. This demonstrates how the major powers like Russia are already embracing the concept of cyber-rattling, akin to nuclear sabre-rattling, thereby challenging the existing security architecture. (Caliskan and Liégeois, 2021). Additionally, the prevailing international protocols and nuclear arms control treaties are limited to the prevention of the nuclear arms race and nuclear war; however, there are no established protocols to manage the sphere of hybrid warfare. The employment of hybrid warfare tactics in recent years, particularly in Ukraine, has shocked the military and defence strategists worldwide. (Patel, 2021).

This paper comparatively investigates the Russian and NATO's hybrid warfare infrastructure in Ukraine through the lens of strategic theory. For Russia, Ukraine is a strategic and geopolitical sphere of influence to deter NATO on its Western border (Renz, 2016). Therefore, this study explores the hybrid warfare techniques employed by the Russian Federation in Ukraine to deter NATO expansion eastwards. The paper addresses three questions: 1. What are the key characteristics of hybrid warfare, and how have they evolved over time? 2. How have Russia and NATO responded to the emergence of hybrid warfare in Ukraine, and what are the key differences in their approaches? 3. To what extent has the development of hybrid warfare infrastructure impacted state security in Ukraine, and what are the potential long-term implications for the country? Hence, the paper is categorised into five sections exploring multi-dimensional aspects of hybrid warfare.

The paper commences with a brief introduction of the term “Hybrid Warfare”, which has remained a subject of debate and discussion over the last ten years. The second section explores multidimensional aspects of hybrid warfare to explore the dynamic nature of the concept. This section briefly sketches the evolution of the term hybrid warfare and its relevance after the Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014. Similarly, the third section theoretically analyses the concept of Hybrid warfare, especially the new tactics that are becoming the cornerstone of the fifth-generation warfare. Likewise, the fourth section comparatively examines the hybrid warfare strategies of the Russian Federation vis-à-vis NATO by taking Ukraine as a case study. The final section examines the threats posed by hybrid warfare to both regional and global security architectures. This section assesses the emerging challenges to international security in the 21st century, particularly the evolving nature of warfare.

Hybrid Warfare: A Brief Overview

The term hybrid warfare is defined from several perspectives as suggested by various scholars and security experts, but it is not just a matter of academic circles; rather, its technical nature transcends

mere definitions (Hoffman, 2014: 13-14). For instance, at the meta-level, the term hybrid warfare refers to a complex strategy that combines conventional military tactics with non-traditional methods, such as misinformation campaigns, cyber attacks and economic coercion to achieve the strategic objectives (Bachmann, 2015). In its essence, it is the muddling application of diplomatic, economic, intelligence, military and criminal means to achieve a political goal (Bratko et al., 2021). With the development in digital technologies, particularly military tech, Hybrid warfare transcended itself beyond the typical concept of “Balance of terror” that remained firmly in the international warfare during the Cold War (Batyuk, 2017).

From a historical standpoint, it refers to the use of both conventional and non-conventional tactics to conduct Military operations (Popescu, 2015). In a broader security perspective, the phenomenon of Hybrid Warfare is not new; rather, it can be traced in the writings of ancient Chinese Military strategist Sun Tzu in the 5th century BC and Greek historian Thucydides. Moreover, in recent history, unnerving armies such as Napoleon's Grand Armée and Hitler's Wehrmacht faced challenges in fighting with the irregular fighters, who used the civilian population as a shield to deter the big battalions (Wither, 2016). Likewise, the guerrilla warfare across various parts of the world, especially during the Cold War, has also contributed to the emergence of hybrid warfare, for instance, in Afghanistan and Iraq, where the US military suffered heavy losses due to guerrilla tactics used by Afghan Taliban and Islamic state of Iraq to fight the coalition forces (Chorent, 2022: 305, 308). In such scenarios, it is impossible for the regular armies to conduct military operations without humanitarian violations, which demonstrates the complex tactical nature of irregular warfare (Weissmann et al., 2021).

For that reason, in the past two decades, Hybrid warfare emerged as an important terminology of contemporary warfare due to its lethal and geostrategic nature (Johnson, 2021: 46-47). During the initial phase, there was no precise definition of hybrid warfare because military strategists attempted to define it as a combination of conventional and irregular forces to intimidate populations and sovereign entities in order to achieve their political objectives (Batyuk, 2017), according to a security analyst. Frank Hoffman's hybrid tactics involve “threats that incorporate a full range of different modes of warfare, including conventional capabilities, irregular tactics and formations, terrorist acts, including indiscriminate violence and coercion, and criminal disorder, conducted by both sides and a variety of non-state actors” (Hoffman, 2014: 16-18). In 2008, Russia used both conventional and unconventional warfare tactics to invade Georgia. In the unconventional sphere, Russia used Abkhazian militias and South Ossetian militias and Russian special defence units², which secretly acted as an operational local defence force on the ground (Fabian, 2019). Likewise, the amalgam of conventional and unconventional means on the battlefield glaringly distinguishes hybrid warfare from all other historical forms of warfare (Monaghan, 2019). In earlier times, the irregular forces were for the secondary operations to the conventional forces on the battlefield (Crueru, 2014).

On the other hand, the 2006 “Israel-Hezbollah” war was a hybrid in nature because Hezbollah showed its flexible logistical might and surprised Israel with its integrated conventional and irregular capabilities during the war. Hezbollah also leveraged media campaigns for global propaganda and psychological warfare against Israel (Kaunert & Wertman, 2020). Moreover, within the sphere of hybrid warfare, communication tactics are part of strategic leverage to demonise the enemy to shape public opinion and have now emerged as a pivotal instrument in state-sponsored warfare, fundamentally transforming the strategies and execution of modern conflicts. (Cox et al., 2012). The emergence of hybrid warfare tactics has significantly enhanced the lethality of non-state actors

² Russia used different special forces units during the seizure of Abkhazia and South Ossetia that includes Russian Airborne Troops, 4th Air Force Command, 42nd Guards Motor Rifle Division and Spetsnaz GRU. See Arsen Araquelov, "Review of the Activities of the Russian Military Forces in Abkhazia and the Tskhinvali Region," Kremlin Roadmap, September 1, 2024, <https://kremlin-roadmap.gfsis.org.ge/monthly-review/display/1606>.

within the context of irregular warfare, such as IS in Iraq and Syria (Wither, 2016). In 2010, the U.S. Defence Review debunked the term hybrid warfare as: “today’s hybrid approaches may involve state adversaries that employ long-drawn-out forms of warfare, possibly using proxy forces to pressure or threaten, or non-state actors using functioning concepts and high-end capabilities traditionally associated with states” (Defense, 2010).

Understanding Hybrid Warfare (Post-2014): From the Perspective of Strategic Theory

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2014 has fundamentally redefined the conceptual framework of hybrid warfare both in the theoretical and practical domains. According to modern warfare experts like Teija Tiilikainen, hybrid tactics proved the most successful in achieving national security objectives by employing coordinated efforts such as disinformation, cyberattacks, and strategic communication i.e., annexation of Crimea by Russia (Lanoszka, 2016; Molnár, 2025: 77). During the invasion of Ukraine in 2014, Russia employed hybrid warfare tactics targeting key critical infrastructure and by supporting local militias in the Eastern Ukrainian regions (Donetsk and Lughansk) (Monaghan, 2016). The Russian hybrid tactics involved the successful employment of both conventional and asymmetrical means to foment political unrest, large-scale cyber operations, economic intimidation and, most significantly, an intense psychological campaign (Batyuk, 2017). certainly, Russian employment of hybrid tactics aligns with the definition of asymmetric warfare by 2015 edition of Military balance, which defines it as “the use of military and non-military tools in an integrated campaign, designed to achieve surprise, seize the initiative and gain psychological as well as physical advantages utilizing diplomatic means; sophisticated and rapid information, electronic and cyber operations; covert and occasionally overt military and intelligence action; and economic pressure” (IISS, 2015: 169, 171).

To address and mitigate the threats and state insecurities arising from hybrid warfare settings, the paper employs an analytical approach through the framework of strategic theory. Throughout history, strategy, whether political, economic or military, has been the central component of statecraft and the art of war (Cox et al., 2012). However, in the last four decades, the evolution strategy as a major theory in the field of International Relations contributed at a larger scale to understanding the contemporary dynamics of international security (Grey, 2015: 50, 56). The emergence of strategic theory as a discursive method of analysis in the field of politics and International Relations is largely attributed to the famous works of renowned political theorists Thomas Schelling and Bernard Brodie (Smith and Stone, 2011). The strategic theory is predominantly concerned with the discourse of state security, particularly with the reasons for the use of force (Milevski, 2016). In this respect, the strategic theory, compared to other approaches to international security, such as securitisation and human security, arguably provides a better understanding of the threats and security challenges emanating from the evolving nature of contemporary warfare (Caliskan, 2019).

The evolving nature of modern warfare, especially hybrid warfare, represents a distinctly unique paradigm, characterised by its multifaceted and adaptive strategies such as asymmetrical and mass disinformation tactics. In recent years, the emergence of information warfare and cyber warfare has ontologically transformed the traditional idea of hybrid warfare both in the theoretical and practical spheres (Bratko et al., 2021; Kyrychenko, 2023). These hybrid tactics were frequently employed by the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) in Syria and Iraq and by the Russian Federation during the invasion of Ukraine (Thiele, 2015). For instance, by employing the disinformation campaigns, ISIS recruited thousands of fighters around the world from Europe, America, and Asia. In a similar fashion, Russia also effectively employed disinformation campaigns as a strategic tool during its conflict with Georgia and the subsequent invasion of Ukraine, significantly influencing the operational and psychological dimensions of these conflicts (Giegerich, 2016; Kaunert and Wertman, 2020). In the tactical spheres, the cyber and electronic warfare has synchronised the Ukrainian

government in their response to the Russian aggression, and likewise, the misinformation campaign globally launched by the Russian satellite channels has grabbed the perception of the world public opinion, besides the staunch criticism by the Western governments (Caliskan, 2019). By using the means of disinformation, Russia shaped and continues to shape public opinion and perceptions both at home and abroad. For that reason, within the hybrid environment, the disinformation campaigns play a tactical role in achieving strategic objectives in the contemporary armed conflicts (Bachmann, 2015).

According to the Russian war experts such as Vladimir Slipchenko and Valery Gerasimov, the psychological and information tactics are employed to achieve victory prior to war, which is referred to as the “New Generation warfare”. According to NATO's Strategic Communications Centre of Excellence, Russia's employment of hybrid tactics such as information superiority in Ukraine significantly contributed to its successful annexation of Crimea in 2014 (Baumann, 2020; Caliskan and Liégeois, 2021). In this respect, strategic theory can unravel the full spectrum of possibilities within the hybrid warfare environment by addressing the evolving and dynamic nature of contemporary armed conflicts.

Modern Warfare: Conventional v/s Asymmetrical

With the dawn of the 21st century, the discourse of security transformed within both theoretical and practical spheres (Weissmann, 2019). Similarly, the classical approaches to national and international security appeared limited due to the new challenges that appeared at the global level, such as terrorism, cross-border migration, human trafficking and organised crime (Smith and Stone, 2011). More importantly, the end of bipolarity after the disintegration of the Soviet Union compelled the strategic thinkers to revisit the classical approaches to security (Nadolski and Fairbanks, 2019). For instance, the emergence of asymmetrical and new techno-centric warfare began posing a new challenge to contemporary security discourse, triggering grounded discussions (Cox et al., 2012). The term asymmetrical warfare appeared with the end of the Cold War, when non-state actors such as terrorist organisations and organised crime groups began using asymmetrical tactics to target the United States and Western countries (Buzan and Wæver, 2009). The new warfare tactics employed by non-state actors include both disinformation campaigns and firepower capabilities with an aim of fomenting political chaos (Gray, 2015: 30). The application of asymmetrical tactics has not been confined to non-state actors; rather, states also began integrating these tactics into their military strategies to achieve their geopolitical and strategic objectives (Caliskan and Liégeois, 2021). The employment of asymmetrical methods has increasingly extended into non-military domains, thereby broadening the ambiguous space between war and peace, which Russia has strategically exploited in the Ukraine conflict to advance its geopolitical objectives (Popescu, 2015). The integration of advanced technologies and asymmetrical tactics at the state level amidst the intensifying geopolitical competition has fundamentally transformed the nature and character of modern warfare. (Weissmann, 2019). For instance, in the past decades, Russia began installing the anti-access area denial capabilities in its Grey Zone in the Eastern and central Europe with an aim of deterring NATO—the anti-access area denial capabilities often refers to as A/2-A/d capabilities aims at shrink the NATO's offensive power not just to make the interventions costlier for the US and its allies in Europe. The deployment of grey zone operations plays a pivotal role in creating deliberate ambiguity and strategic manoeuvring below the threshold of conventional warfare to achieve political or territorial gains without triggering overt conflict. The Grey Zone operations have parallels with hybrid Warfare tactics—since they blend military, informational, economic, and cyber tactics to exploit vulnerabilities, destabilise adversaries, and advance geopolitical objectives in the contested space between peace and war (Dalsjö and Jonsson, 2021).

The asymmetrical tactics, such as cyber operations, disinformation campaigns, and psychological warfare, put one's strength against the weakness of the other (adversary). Consequently, the evolving

concept of "war" now encompasses cultural, social, legal, psychological, and moral dimensions, where traditional military power increasingly appears less decisive (Farnsworth et al., 2014). The definition of hybrid warfare in the West closely aligns with the Chinese concept of unrestricted warfare, as articulated in the book *Unrestricted Warfare* by two colonels of the People's Liberation Army. The book proposes innovative methods for a nation like China to counter a militarily superior adversary, such as the United States, by leveraging non-traditional strategies (Lasica, 2009). Like hybrid warfare, unrestricted warfare also involves the use of a multi-layered tactical means, both military and non-military, to strike the enemy during the time of conflict (Cruceru, 2014). One of the authors stated in an interview that "the first rule of unrestricted warfare is that there are no rules, with nothing forbidden."—In the practical sphere, China has frequently used these unrestricted tactics for the territorial claims in the South China Sea in the past decade and a half (Zhang, 2019).

Ukraine as the Victim of Hybrid Warfare

Russian military experts have consistently maintained secrecy regarding their use of hybrid warfare tactics aimed at countering NATO (Baumann, 2020). Moreover, the Russian military elite are acutely aware of the U.S. grand strategy in Europe, which seeks to contain Russia by stripping off its sphere of influence in the post-Soviet space (Barbrook, 2000). The American strategists crafted this multidimensional pre-emptive strategy during the last decades of the Soviet Union to keep Russia as a zonal power within the Eurasian landmass (Mazepus et al., 2015). And following the disintegration of the Soviet Union, the U.S. revived a similar strategy, which, according to Russian military experts, exploited Russia's vulnerabilities to further destabilise it internally. (Thomas, 2016). Since the beginning of NATO's eastward expansion in 2004, Russia consistently expressed its security concerns and warned the West not to cross its red line. Consequently, the outbreak of the Orange Revolution in Ukraine in the same years further deepened the security fears of Russia (Klein, 2015). The growing political unrest in the post-Soviet space compelled Russian military elites to develop a new strategy to counter NATO's influence (Wilson, 2010). Hence, the covert hybrid operations in Ukraine and the annexation of Crimea in 2014 were integral to Russia's new defence strategy, designed to offset NATO's perceived hybrid warfare against Russia. This new hybrid warfare strategy was sophisticated and multi-layered, encompassing both conventional warfare tactics and asymmetrical methods, such as cyberattacks, disinformation campaigns, and psychological operations, to destabilise adversaries from within (Popescu, 2015). The Western experts of Russia, like Alexander Cooley, referred to Russia's new hybrid warfare strategy as the "Gerasimov Doctrine", pioneered by the incumbent Russian Chief of Staff General Valery Gerasimov. Gerasimov defines the New Generation warfare as: "the broad use of political, economic, informational, humanitarian and other non-military means ... supplemented by civil disorder among the local population and concealed armed forces" (Gerasimov and Coalson, 2014: 1; Orenstein, 2019).

According to Gerasimov, the twenty-first century warfare is very different from the typical ones because it involves much complex strategies that range from economy to technology. Russia successfully employed mass disinformation and covert tactics to foment civil unrest in the eastern regions of Ukraine (Monaghan, 2016). Thus, in the case of Russia, the new generation warfare is associated with the Gerasimov Doctrine that aims at securing the Russian realm in Eastern and Central Europe (Rumer, 2019: 15-16). The aim of this kind of "warfare" is to apply psychological pressure to cause the downfall of the target state from within so that the political objectives of the conflict can be achieved without fighting – the acme of strategic skill according to Sun Tzu (Monaghan, 2019). During the annexation of Crimea, Russia used the same strategy to destabilise Ukraine across the critical strategic spheres.

Case Analysis: Russia vis-à-vis NATO's Hybrid Operations in Ukraine

Since the outbreak of colour revolutions in the post-Soviet space, a new debate surrounding national security has emerged among the Russian political and security circles (Forsberg and Herd, 2015). The escalating political instability along Russia's borders prompted Russian military strategists to develop a new strategy to address the emerging security threats (Giegerich, 2016). And the issue of national security became a central topic of debate and discussion within Russian security circles, reminiscent of the disintegration of the Soviet Union (Cross, 2015). Russia employed this new strategy in the form of the hybrid warfare operation in 2014, when it annexed Crimea through a combination of military intervention and a controversial referendum, while simultaneously sponsoring separatist groups in eastern Ukraine's Donbas region to destabilise the country and counter its pro-Western orientation (Mazepus et al., 2015). Since then, the conflict has escalated into a protracted armed conflict, with both Russia and NATO employing a mix of conventional and unconventional tactics, including hybrid warfare strategies (Wilson, 2010). Hybrid warfare has been used by both Russia and NATO-aligned forces, primarily in the form of information operations, cyberattacks, economic pressure, and proxy warfare.

Russia

The Russia pivot towards developing a new national and regional strategy began taking shape during the late 1990s. It was Yevgeny Primakov, who served as the Prime Minister of Russia from 1998 to 1999, who advocated for a new Russian grand security strategy to overcome threats both at home and abroad, which later came to be known as the Primakov doctrine (DeLong, 2020). The Primakov doctrine insists on developing a new multi-layered and complex security infrastructure to counter the emerging new security challenges to Russia (Gurganus and Rumer, 2019). Primakov Doctrine opines that the disintegration of the Soviet Union brought new domestic and regional security challenges for Russia, particularly in its adjacent front yard and backyard, which demand a new security strategy (Rumer, 2019). Since the early 2000s, Russia has been developing and implementing new strategies to preserve its spheres of influence in response to perceived geopolitical challenges—Russian actions in Georgia and Ukraine validate this new strategy. Especially, Russia's hybrid infrastructure in Ukraine demonstrates its effectiveness, which includes a range of military, political, and economic measures, including support for separatist movements in eastern Ukraine, disinformation campaigns, and strategic economic leverage, designed to destabilise Ukraine and maintain Russian influence in the region. Table 1 below illustrates some of the key determinants of Russia's hybrid infrastructure in Ukraine, along with brief descriptions and references.

Table 1: Determinants of Russia's Hybrid Infrastructure in Ukraine

Determinant	Description	Reference
Military intervention	Russia has intervened militarily in Ukraine, including through the annexation of Crimea in 2014 and the ongoing conflict in eastern Ukraine. Russia has provided military support to separatist groups, including through the deployment of Russian military personnel and the provision of weapons and other military equipment.	Council on Foreign Relations - Ukraine Crisis: A Timeline
Political support	Russia has provided political support to separatist movements in Ukraine, including through statements and declarations expressing support for their efforts to secede from Ukraine. Russia has also sought to undermine the legitimacy of the Ukrainian government and create political divisions within Ukraine.	Council on Foreign Relations - Ukraine Crisis: A Timeline
Economic assistance	Russia has provided economic assistance to separatist movements in Ukraine, including through the provision of financial support and the establishment of economic ties with separatist-controlled	Council on Foreign Relations - Ukraine Crisis: A Timeline

	areas. Russia has also imposed economic sanctions on Ukraine in an effort to exert pressure on the Ukrainian government.	
Cyber-attacks and disinformation campaigns	Russia has conducted cyber-attacks and disinformation campaigns in Ukraine, with the aim of undermining the Ukrainian government and creating confusion and instability. These efforts have included the use of social media and other online platforms to spread false information and sow discord within Ukraine.	Council on Foreign Relations - Ukraine Crisis: A Timeline

Note: Russia's hybrid infrastructure in Ukraine is multifaceted and has evolved over time in response to changing circumstances. These determinants are some of the key factors that have shaped Russia's approach to exerting influence in Ukraine and supporting separatist movements.

The relevance of the Primakov Doctrine became vivid after 2004, when NATO began expanding towards the eastern borders of Russia (Kolossoff and Turovsky, 2007). The Russian military elites perceived NATO's eastward expansion as an existential threat to the security of Russia and became obsessed with the security of the Russian sphere of influence in the heartland (Clover, 1999). Nonetheless, NATO's eastward expansion marked a critical turning point that compelled Russian elites to reassess and reshape their strategic approach to relations with the West in the subsequent years. (Fabian, 2019). Russia blamed NATO, particularly America, for creating political unrest in the post-Soviet space by sponsoring colour revolutions (Freire, 2018). Moreover, in the minds of Russian security elites, NATO's expansion of its military infrastructure into the post-Soviet space constitutes a breach of assurances and a strategic betrayal of commitments made to Mikhail Gorbachev during the dissolution of the Soviet Union (Larrabee, 2010). This perceived security violation played a pivotal role in shaping the strategic posture of the Russian Federation after 2004, fuelling tensions and influencing its adoption of hybrid warfare tactics to counter Western influence in the post-Soviet space (Forsberg and Herd, 2015).

NATO

Following the disintegration of the Soviet Union, NATO began developing new contingency plans for its expansion into the post-Soviet space (Roberts, 2017). The primary manifestation of NATO's expansionist strategy occurred in 1999, when the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland joined the alliance, significantly alarming Russian political elites and provoking strong indignation among the Russian military leadership (Klein, 2015). Due to its expansionist plans, NATO gradually began posing a graveyard challenge to the Russian sphere of influence in Eastern and Central Europe, which forced Russia to develop counter-measures (Thomas, 2016). In response to NATO's eastward expansion, particularly following the accession of the Baltic states—Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania—into the alliance in 2004, Russia began formulating new strategies to counter the perceived security threats along its western border and in the Baltic region. The security of the Baltic states poses a significant challenge for NATO, as these nations host substantial Russian-speaking populations, which Russia could exploit through information warfare and hybrid tactics to destabilise these geopolitically vulnerable states (Kramer, 2003).

The new Russian strategy began manifesting itself in an asymmetric manner, employing multi-layered hybrid tactics such as disinformation campaigns, cyber operations, and psychological warfare to undermine adversaries and advance its geopolitical objectives in contested regions (Renz B., 2019). However, the primary battleground between NATO and Russia emerged in Ukraine, where NATO has been deeply engaged since the late 1990s, establishing covert operational centres to fund and support anti-Russian political groups, thereby intensifying geopolitical tensions and contributing to the escalation of hybrid warfare in the region. Table 2 below illustrates NATO's hybrid warfare strategy in Ukraine vis-à-vis Russia.

Table 2: Determinants of NATO's Hybrid Infrastructure

Determinant	Description	Reference
Military assistance	NATO has provided military assistance to Ukraine, including training, equipment, and advisory support. This assistance is aimed at helping Ukraine to build its defence capabilities and improve its ability to respond to threats.	NATO - Ukraine: Building stability and security in Eastern Europe
Political support	NATO has expressed political support for Ukraine, including through statements and declarations condemning Russian aggression and calling for the respect of Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity.	NATO - Ukraine: Building stability and security in Eastern Europe
Economic assistance	NATO has provided economic assistance to Ukraine, including through various programs and initiatives aimed at supporting Ukraine's economic development and reform efforts.	NATO - Ukraine: Building stability and security in Eastern Europe
Cybersecurity cooperation	NATO has worked with Ukraine to improve its cybersecurity capabilities and defend against cyber threats. This has included sharing expertise and knowledge, as well as providing technical assistance and training.	NATO - Cybersecurity cooperation with Ukraine

Note: It is important to note that NATO's hybrid infrastructure in Ukraine is multifaceted and has evolved over time in response to changing circumstances. These determinants are some of the key factors that have shaped NATO's approach to supporting Ukraine.

As delineated in Table 2, NATO's hybrid warfare infrastructure in Ukraine encompasses a range of military, political, and economic measures designed to counter Russia's influence and compete across multiple domains in the region. These measures are designed to strengthen Ukraine's defence capabilities, promote stability and security in the region, and counter Russian efforts to destabilise Ukraine (Lanoszka, 2016). The key tactical measures include military assistance, such as training, equipment, and advisory support, to boost Ukraine's defence capabilities and improve its ability to respond to threats (Cross, 2015). It also includes politico-cum diplomatic support, such as statements and declarations condemning Russian aggression and calling for the respect of Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity (Abbott, 2016). In the past decade, NATO has extended significant economic assistance to Ukraine through various programs and initiatives designed to bolster the country's economic development and reform efforts (Shea and Jaroszewicz, 2021). Additionally, NATO has collaborated closely with Ukraine to enhance its cybersecurity capabilities, providing technical assistance, training, and expertise to strengthen defences against cyber threats and counter hybrid warfare tactics in the region (Burton, 2015). This demonstrates NATO's hybrid warfare infrastructure in Ukraine is multifaceted and has evolved over time in response to changing circumstances (Shea, 2017). These hybrid measures are part of NATO's broader efforts to support Ukraine and promote stability and security in the region.

Prior to the 2014 events in Ukraine, NATO underestimated the sophistication and efficacy of Russia's hybrid warfare mechanisms. The annexation of Crimea in 2014 sent shockwaves across the West, as it revealed the extent to which NATO had miscalculated the strategic depth and impact of Russia's hybrid warfare tactics, which combined military operations, disinformation campaigns, and covert actions to achieve geopolitical objectives (Biersack and O'Lear, 2014). This miscalculation prompted both the EU and NATO over the past decade to engage in high-level consultations aimed at strengthening communication security and countering hybrid threats across the European continent (Bratko et al., 2021). Following Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014, NATO member states intensified their efforts to develop infrastructure to counter hybrid warfare in Eastern Europe (Gardner, 2016). These geopolitical events involving NATO and Russia proved the efficacy of hybrid

warfare as a tangible reality at the heart of Europe, since both NATO and Russia strive to safeguard their respective spheres of influence in this critical region.

Implications of Russia and NATO Hybrid Warfare Operations on Global Security

Over the past two decades, the nature of warfare has undergone a profound transformation, driven by advancements in weapons technology and the emergence of cyberspace as a critical domain, as demonstrated by the evolving character of conflict in Ukraine in 2014 (Boot et al., 2015). Thus, one can infer that while the fundamental nature of warfare remains constant, its *modus operandi* has evidently evolved significantly over the past decade (Batyuk, 2017). The adoption of new military technologies, particularly in the tactical sphere, shows that modern warfare is not being fought on the battlefield, but rather in the boardrooms—the high-speed interest and the techno-centric warfare innovation in cyberspace has become a major element of modern warfare (Giegerich, 2016). The new generation warfare, often referred to as hybrid warfare/ asymmetrical warfare in military discourses across the West, is the living reality of our time (Johnson, 2018). Consequently, traditional approaches to national and international security are increasingly inadequate in addressing the evolving dynamics of modern warfare because its asymmetric nature undermines the traditional notions of “security” at the structural level (Lasica, 2009).

Unlike traditional warfare, hybrid warfare involves both conventional and unconventional tactics and methods. For this reason, the security theorists and military experts are compelled to rethink their conventional approaches to warfare both in the theoretical and practical spheres (Cox et al., 2011). It is evident that hybrid warfare poses significant challenges and threats to state security across multiple domains, including territorial integrity, political stability, and sovereignty (Filipec, 2019). Furthermore, the mechanisms of hybrid warfare, which include disinformation campaigns, cyberattacks, and economic coercion, have rendered the preservation of sovereignty and national security a formidable challenge not only for smaller states but also for major powers (Bachmann, 2015). Perhaps, this induces the security experts and policymakers to rethink and revisit the discourse of national and international security because the asymmetric nature of the hybrid warfare potentially endangers the existing security paradigms of states at the global level (Fridman, 2017).

The annexation of Crimea by the Russian Federation in 2014 instigated a renewed discourse within Western security forums, heightening apprehensions regarding the ramifications for national security and the multifaceted challenges introduced by hybrid warfare methodologies (Giles, 2016; Biersack and O’Lear, 2014). In response to Russia’s complex hybrid warfare infrastructure, Western countries, particularly NATO member states, have initiated the development of their own hybrid warfare capabilities to counter Russian strategic manoeuvres (Rusnáková, 2017). Consequently, the dynamic and evolving nature of hybrid warfare has prompted nations to modernise their defence capabilities to address emerging threats posed by these complex strategies (Batyuk, 2017). Because hybrid warfare encompasses highly sophisticated and often covert tactics, closely intertwined with asymmetrical methods and psychological operations, which challenge traditional security frameworks (Mumford, 2020). Compared to traditional warfare tactics, hybrid warfare aims at destabilising and paralysing the state from within through disinformation campaigns and psychological actions (Oguz, 2016). Practically, Russia employed the same hybrid tactics to paralyse Ukraine and annexe Crimea in 2014 (Biersack and O’Lear, 2014). Therefore, the complex security dynamics and multifaceted nature of hybrid warfare are compelling the defence sectors of nations to enhance and streamline their security infrastructure to effectively address the evolving challenges of modern armed conflicts. (Cox et al., 2011). The existing state security policies worldwide exhibit significant deficiencies in addressing the multifaceted shocks and threats emanating from the hybrid warfare environment. From a global security perspective, the discourse surrounding state security has become a central topic of debate and discussion among security experts and military strategists. Moreover, the emergence of fifth-generation warfare necessitates the development of a new

international security policy framework to counter the escalating challenges to state sovereignty posed by hybrid tactics.

Conclusion

The dawn of hybrid warfare has already compelled military theorists and security experts to revisit the discourse of both national and international security. The robust existence of Russian hybrid warfare infrastructure vis-à-vis NATO in the post-Soviet space is threatening the regional security in Europe by increasing the chances of direct military confrontation. Evidently, the traditional approach to international security certainly appears limited in understanding the complex and tactical nature of modern warfare that transcends the conventional security horizons. As a result, to assess the discourse of state security in the 21st century, security experts and strategists must develop a new security framework to overcome the threats posed by the hybrid warfare settings. A comparative study of Russia's and NATO's hybrid infrastructure in Ukraine highlights the different approaches that these two actors have taken to address the challenges posed by a hybrid warfare environment. Russia has pursued a more aggressive and interventionist approach, using military force and other means to exert influence in Ukraine and support separatist movements. NATO has taken a more defensive and supportive approach, providing military assistance, political support, and economic assistance to Ukraine in an effort to strengthen its defence capabilities and promote stability and security in the region. The future of state security will likely continue to be shaped by the challenges posed by hybrid warfare that obliges states to adapt and develop new strategies and capabilities to defend against such threats, while also working to preserve the rules and norms that govern international relations. The comparative study of Russian and NATO's hybrid infrastructure in Ukraine provides valuable insights into the different approaches that states can take to address these challenges and highlights the importance of security discourses to understand the evolving nature of modern warfare.

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